

Small
= good

Pursuing
growth

meaningful
exchange

Distribute
tasks

Honor your
Needs

No

Care for
your health

Science
=
Socio-technical

Mentorship

Community
management

Keynote Malvika Sharan

Be strategic
about time

Clarity

=
Kindness

Decision making
strategies

Importance of
showing up

Open Leadership

Self-advocacy

Volunteering

Public
participation
↓
recognition

- Networking
- New skills
- Career options

Intentional
Inclusion

Language
+ culture

funds

- Short Format
- Training** @Astra Zeneca
- On Demand
- Online + several time zones

INDUSTRY

Keynote

Education is a Community Sport

ACADEMIA

- Short Format
 - Training** @Harvard
 - open + collaborative content on GitHub
-

Radhika Khetani

Similar

Different

Internal + external communities	Industry:	Academia
Challenge: Learner Motivation	↓ time	↑
	↑	Dayment possibilities ↓

Pay or reward trainers
Industry should contribute back

SUGGESTIONS

More dedicated time for learning
Develop training communities in industry

Keynote

Yanina Bellini Saibene
 R₅OpenSci

numbers + stories matter
 are we doing things right? funding